

**Appendix: “The Pragmatic Versatility of *Mirá si* + Periphrastic Future:
Polyphony and Discourse Frames in Argentine Spanish”**

Mark Hoff

Queens College CUNY

This appendix provides glosses for linguistic expressions or cultural references that may not be familiar to all audiences.

- (3) *Nona*: Italian grandmother (*nonna*). *Pelotudeces yankees*: stupid American things.
- (4) *Berretada*: cheap crap
- (7) *Descansar*: to make fun of. *Facturas*: pastries.
- (12) *Dejar a gamba*: to let down
- (20) *Bancar*: to support, back up
- (22) *Boludeces*: stupid things
- (36) *Nenazo*: overgrown kid
- (39) *Les pibes*: gender-inclusive language for “kids”. *Puan*: campus of the University of Buenos Aires, home to the Faculty of Philosophy and Letters.
- (45) *Cba*: Córdoba
- (46) *UBA*: University of Buenos Aires. *Guita*: money. *Laburante*: working-class person
- (47) *9 de Julio*: Argentine Independence Day
- (48) *Bronca*: anger.
- (49) *PRO*: Propuesta Republicana. *CABA*: Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires. *Ladrillo sapo*: hollow, cheap brick.
- (51) *Posta*: honestly, for real
- (53) *Tl*: Twitter timeline
- (55) *Una banda*: many
- (57) *Socialista amarillo*: fake Socialist aligned with PRO party
- (60) *Furia*: Juliana “Furia” Scaglione, contestant on *Gran Hermano*
- (61) *Salamín*: doofus

- (67) *Sachistas de Sacha*: supporters of racecar driver Sacha Fenestraz
- (69) *Chusmear*: check out, snoop around in
- (71) *Capo*: boss
- (78) *Macrismo*: center-right politics of Mauricio Macri. *Afano*: theft.
- (81) *Picantear*: stir things up, cause trouble. *Icardi*, *China Suárez*, *Yanina*: Argentine celebrities.
- (85) *Flor de ansioso*: anxious as hell
- (91) *Hincha de Vélez*: fan of the Vélez football club